

MarkerName	CHS EA	EPIC	FHS	lnCHIANTI	KORA	LBC1921	LBC1936	NAS	RS	WHI case EA	WHI control EA	ARIC	CHS AA	GENOA	GTP	WHI case AA	WHI control AA
cg00159243	-0.0026	-0.0021	-0.00295	-0.00603	-0.00154	-0.00364	-0.00381	-0.0041	-0.00261	-0.00381	-0.00231	-0.00415	-0.00337	-	-0.00375	-0.00554	-0.00083
cg00812761	0.0051	0.00018	0.00192	-0.00031	0.00326	-0.00162	0.00015	0.0024	0.00552	0.00378	0.0024	0.00401	0.00496	-	0.00364	0.004	0.00136
cg00851028	0.00536	0.00153	0.00207	0.0018	0.00219	0.00421	0.00311	0.00209	0.00305	0.00613	0.00158	0.00478	0.00361	-	0.00371	0.0033	0.00426
cg01059398	-0.0084	-0.00486	-0.00391	-0.00106	-0.00593	-0.00216	0.00057	-0.00583	-0.00403	-0.00036	-0.00367	-0.00601	-0.00763	-	-0.00272	-0.01095	-0.00656
cg01409343	-0.003	-0.00515	-0.00426	-0.00246	-0.00414	-0.00635	0.00223	-0.01063	-0.00091	-0.00084	-0.00287	-0.01151	-0.00377	-	-0.00101	-0.00697	-0.00534
cg02003183	0.00645	0.00256	0.00518	3.00E-05	0.00303	0.01044	0.00863	0.00537	0.00471	0.00771	0.00627	0.00675	0.0055	-	0.00098	0.00333	0.00319
cg02341197	0.00532	0.0044	0.00285	-0.00197	0.00417	-6.00E-04	-0.00562	0.00488	0.00138	0.00614	0.00513	0.00521	0.00086	-	0.00561	0.00829	0.00027
cg02481950	0.00434	0.00194	0.00238	0.00201	0.00223	0.00191	0.00187	0.0049	0.001	0.0038	0.00285	0.00347	0.00129	-	0.00351	0.00449	0.00413
cg02650017	-0.0044	-0.00405	-0.00216	-0.00243	-0.00152	-0.00095	-0.00228	-0.00188	-0.00306	-0.00173	-0.0027	-0.00108	0.00139	-	-0.00294	-0.00181	-0.00112
cg02734358	-0.00477	-0.00561	-0.00381	-0.00509	-0.00616	-0.01287	0.00536	-0.00394	-0.00642	-0.00249	-0.00813	-0.00673	-0.00089	-	-0.00087	-0.00696	-0.00492
cg03128029	-0.00067	-0.00302	-0.00242	-0.00311	-0.00241	-0.00283	-0.00066	-0.00869	-0.00218	-0.00169	-0.00564	-0.00617	-0.00404	-	0.00032	-0.00191	-0.00097
cg03957124	-0.00359	-0.00195	-0.00265	-0.00161	-0.00485	0.00156	-0.00235	-0.0042	-0.00268	-0.00069	-0.00452	-0.00499	-0.00541	-	-0.00098	-0.00054	-0.00105
cg04523589	0.00256	0.00034	0.00262	0.00154	0.0024	0.00283	0.00287	0.0032	8.00E-04	0.00449	0.0038	0.00305	0.00558	0.00174	0.00676	0.00505	0.00111
cg04987734	0.00724	-1.00E-04	0.00522	-0.001	0.00375	0.0068	0.00183	0.00605	0.0029	0.00875	0.00447	0.00775	0.00646	-	-0.00073	0.00516	0.00092
cg05316065	-0.00188	-0.00405	-0.00196	-0.00352	-0.00429	-0.00178	-0.0043	-0.00389	-0.00222	-0.00057	-0.00404	-0.00576	0.00102	-0.00687	-0.00469	-0.00235	-0.00509
cg05575921	0.00224	-0.00687	-0.00496	-0.01077	-0.0072	-0.0061	-0.00739	-0.004	-0.0095	-0.00571	-0.00369	-0.00866	-0.00302	-	-0.0036	-4.00E-05	-0.00726
cg06126421	-0.00682	-0.00605	-0.00488	-0.00608	-0.00749	-0.00219	-0.00989	-0.00211	-0.00379	-0.00439	-0.00596	-0.00782	9.00E-05	-	0.00064	-0.00537	-0.00092
cg06192883	0.00626	0.00489	0.00471	0.00218	0.00377	0.00778	0.00482	0.00434	0.00332	0.00601	0.00662	0.00766	0.00649	-	0.00393	0.00881	0.00712
cg06690548	0.00211	-0.00122	-0.01023	-0.00201	-0.00626	-0.00012	-0.00495	-0.0131	-0.00249	-0.00689	-0.0077	-0.00405	-0.00283	-0.00251	-0.00228	-0.00099	-0.00301
cg07094298	-0.00343	-0.00637	-0.00521	-0.00221	-0.00808	-0.00895	-0.00033	-0.00239	-0.00611	-0.00672	-0.00431	-0.00682	-0.00624	-	0.00169	-0.00871	-0.0036
cg07573872	-0.00941	-0.00306	-0.00539	-0.00373	-0.00521	-0.00201	-0.00732	-0.01102	-0.00423	-0.00451	-0.00537	-0.00863	-0.00591	-	0.00685	-0.00896	-0.00637
cg08548559	-0.00346	-0.00116	-0.00322	-0.00551	-0.00523	-0.00154	0.00074	-0.0036	-0.00429	-0.0057	-0.00675	-0.00552	-0.00335	-	-0.0023	-0.00592	-0.00449
cg09182678	-0.00245	-0.00288	-0.00143	-0.00386	-	-0.00349	-0.00787	-0.00042	-0.00482	-0.00065	-0.00238	-0.0023	0.00041	-	-0.0023	-0.00174	-0.00191
cg10636246	-0.00246	-0.00672	-0.00739	-0.00516	-0.00693	-3.00E-04	-0.00568	-0.01065	-0.00608	-0.00649	-0.00781	-0.0115	0.00104	-	-0.00336	-0.00722	-0.00923
cg12053291	0.00113	0.0019	0.0039	-2.00E-05	0.00315	0.00134	0.00599	0.00476	0.00186	0.00386	0.0016	0.00451	-3.00E-05	-	0.00322	0.00245	0.00487
cg12054453	-0.0051	-0.00483	-0.00855	-0.00952	-0.01013	0.00072	-0.01254	-0.01425	-0.00654	-0.00141	-0.01008	-0.01584	-0.00755	-	0.00193	-0.01223	-0.00923
cg12269535	-0.00239	-0.00456	-0.00207	-0.00374	-0.00378	-0.0102	-0.00052	-0.00168	-0.00263	-0.00091	-0.00346	-0.00518	-0.00502	-	0.00235	-0.00454	-0.00675
cg12992827	-0.00353	-0.00228	-0.00844	-0.00769	-0.00661	-0.01053	0.00311	-0.01077	-0.0015	-0.00455	-0.00856	-0.01055	-0.00112	-	-0.00393	-0.01113	-0.00886
cg13585930	-0.0031	-0.00421	-0.00254	-0.00594	-0.00436	-0.00411	-0.00646	-0.00382	-0.00468	-0.00657	-0.00607	-0.0064	-	-	-0.00085	-0.00393	-0.00573
cg15020801	0.00525	0.00322	0.00221	0.00288	0.00115	0.00486	0.00498	0.00534	0.00094	0.00288	0.00478	0.00377	0.00559	-	-8.00E-05	0.00242	0.00324
cg15310871	0.00238	0.00323	0.00338	0.00226	0.00106	0.00715	0.00135	0.00207	0.00065	0.00175	0.00179	0.00344	0.00351	-	0.0017	0.00132	0.00169
cg15551881	0.00253	0.00195	0.00378	-0.00053	0.00486	0.00553	0.01334	0.00734	0.00194	0.00407	0.00458	0.00571	0.00614	0.00412	0.00968	0.00616	0.00215
cg15721584	0.00013	0.00942	0.00493	0.00091	-	-	0.00853	0.00383	0.00083	0.00083	0.01541	0.00626	0.01305	-	0.00106	0.00718	0.01032
cg16936953	-0.00759	-0.00537	-0.00846	-0.0073	-0.00978	-0.00542	-0.00631	-0.0152	-0.00467	-0.00243	-0.00849	-0.01681	-0.00837	-	0.00044	-0.01128	-0.00963
cg17501210	-0.00572	-0.00599	-0.00722	-0.00297	-0.00838	-0.00697	-0.00184	-0.00614	-0.00551	-0.00529	-0.01064	-0.00648	-0.00231	-	-0.00456	-0.01355	-0.00092
cg17980786	0.00531	0.00188	0.00228	4.00E-04	0.00272	0.00445	0.00171	0.00138	0.00339	0.00361	0.00516	0.00603	0.00531	-	0.00591	0.00467	0.00438
cg18181703	-0.00755	-0.00426	-0.00522	-0.00359	-0.00651	-0.00722	-0.00425	-0.00543	-0.00518	-0.00398	-0.00301	-0.01212	-0.01103	-	-0.00324	-0.00401	-0.00653
cg18608055	-0.00162	-0.00528	-0.00465	-0.00885	-0.00479	-0.00542	0.00058	-0.00398	-0.00419	-0.00244	-0.00473	-0.01017	-0.00579	-	-0.00046	-0.00727	-0.00703
cg18663307	0.00023	0.00162	0.0035	0.00236	0.00329	0.00358	0.00367	0.00511	0.00204	0.00169	0.00223	0.00374	0.00519	-	0.00554	0.00491	0.00629
cg18942579	-0.00346	-0.00362	-0.00625	-0.00635	-0.00806	-0.00689	0.00695	-0.00983	-0.00438	-0.00218	-0.00432	-0.01567	-0.0057	-	-0.00122	-0.00862	-0.00386
cg19769147	-0.00055	0.00263	0.00302	7.00E-04	0.00262	0.00371	0.00548	0.00239	0.00281	0.00461	0.00364	0.0034	-0.00036	-	0.00362	0.00222	0.00229
cg19821297	-0.00452	-0.00601	-0.0046	-0.00471	-0.00738	-0.00541	0.00267	-0.00718	-0.00455	-0.00353	-0.00562	-0.00767	-0.00062	-	0.00329	-0.00892	-0.00375
cg20995564	-0.00567	-0.00251	-0.00549	-0.00639	-0.0061	-0.0073	-0.00154	-0.00871	-0.00247	-0.00469	-0.00733	-0.01198	-0.00355	-	-0.00106	-0.0073	-0.0103
cg21429551	0.00155	-0.00165	-0.0058	-0.00917	-	-0.0043	-0.00451	-0.00715	-0.00853	-0.01002	-0.01789	-0.00972	-0.00632	-	0.00059	-0.00601	-0.01085
cg22749855	-0.00302	-0.00277	-0.00284	-0.00064	-0.00286	0.00098	-0.00179	-0.004	-0.00078	-0.00126	-0.00346	-0.00419	-0.00297	-	-0.00177	-0.00305	-0.00407
cg23761815	0.00138	0.00261	0.00232	0.00116	0.00279	0.00414	0.00044	0.00209	0.00159	0.00567	0.00121	0.0026	0.00448	-	0.00244	0.00515	0.00156
cg24174557	-0.00411	-0.00195	-0.00298	-0.00583	-	-	-0.00509	-0.00488	-0.00563	-0.00582	-0.00685	-0.00278	-	-	8.00E-04	-0.00732	-0.00271
cg25325512	-0.00645	-0.00383	-0.00311	-8.00E-04	-0.00541	-0.00137	-0.00567	-0.00551	-0.00127	0.00217	0.00108	-0.0069	-0.00583	-	-0.00458	-0.00124	-0.0045
cg25392060	0.00624	0.00481	0.00226	-0.00236	0.00201	0.00409	0.0012	0.00157	0.0029	0.00483	0.00428	0.00349	0.00252	-	0.00389	0.00589	0.00193
cg26470501	0.00078	-0.00285	-0.00464	-0.00243	-0.00634	-0.00634	-0.00781	-0.00394	-0.00394	-0.00295	-0.00426	-0.00671	-0.00479	-	0.00094	-0.00466	-0.00461
cg26610247	0.00263	0.00366	0.0033	-0.0026	0.00193	0.00774	-0.00029	0.00168	0.00479	0.00232	0.00491	0.00396	0.00576	-	0.00688	0.00392	0.00234
cg26804423	0.00393	0.00197	0.00364	0.00056	0.00365	0.00396	-0.00076	0.00187	0.00097	0.00453	0.00156	0.00397	0.00396	-	0.0057	0.00369	0.00109
cg26846781	0.00119	0.00199	0.00181	0.00138	0.00383	-0.00192	0.002	0.00385	0.00148	0.00433	0.00162	0.0036	3.00E-05	-	0.00499	0.00376	0.00248
cg27023597	-0.00667	-0.00713	-0.0052	-0.00671	-	-	-0.00974	-0.00208	-0.00284	-0.00284	-0.0025	-0.01062	-0.00433	-	0.00226	-0.00936	-0.00439
cg27050612	0.00014	-0.00267	-0.00183	-0.00204	-0.00177	-0.0054	-0.0034	-0.00054	-0.00269	-0.00154	-0.00135	-0.00308	-0.00318	-	-0.002	-0.00254	-0.0031
cg27184903	0.00237	0.00172	0.00311	0.00104	0.00166	0.00125	0.00283	0.00024	-	0.00728	0.00215	0.00389	0.00654	-	0.00448	0.00823	0.00665
cg27469606	-0.00191	-0.00161	-0.002	-0.00234	-0.00361	-0.00219	-0.00365	-0.00345	-0.00018	0.00067	-0.00274	-0.0022	-0.00173	-	0.00026	-0.00346	-